

Supplementary Material for: "Design and development of a lower cost, customizable simulator for resuscitative endovascular balloon occlusion of the aorta (REBOA) training"
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Supplementary Figure 1: 3D modeled bifurcation engineering drawing

This engineering drawing was used to produce the aortic bifurcation used in the simulation.

Supplementary Figure 2: CAD Schematic of Groin (left) and Real Groin Piece within Device (right)

The groin design used a 3D printed component that was reproducible but also maintained US usability and physiologic fidelity.

Supplementary Figure 3: Outline of fluid system

The fluid started at the reservoir and continued to cycle through the entire system. As time went on, the pressure decreased unless the balloon was inflated. After the balloon was inflated, the main path was blocked causing pressure to increase. This pressure increase signaled for an electronic valve to activate, opening a backflow system that allowed for the fluid to go through an alternate path since the main path would be blocked by the balloon. This valve was a solenoid valve that opened when 12V was applied and remained closed otherwise.

Supplementary Table 1: Equations used to solve for the pressure drop

Description	Equation
Flow Rate Assumption	flowRate = 2.4 L/min
Given Values	Q = 2.4 L/min
	D = 2.3 cm
	L = 45 cm
	$\mu = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$
	$\rho = 1060 \text{ kg/m}^3$
Conversion of Flow Rate	$Q = 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
Conversion of Diameter	D = 0.023 m
Conversion of Length	L = 0.45 m
Viscosity Conversion	$\mu = 0.003 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{s})$
Cross-Sectional Area	$A = \pi \times D^2$
	A = 0.002 m ²
Velocity	$V = Q / A$
	V = 0.024 m/s
Reynolds Number	$Re = (\rho \times V \times D) / \mu$
	Re = 195.599
Pressure Drop	$\Delta P = (128 \times \mu \times L \times Q) / (\pi \times D^4)$
	$\Delta P = 7.862 \text{ Pa}$
	$\Delta P = 0.001 \text{ psi}$

Supplementary Table 1 illustrates the calculations and conversions related to the flow rate and pressure drop within the system. The assumed flow rate is 2.4 L/min, with given values including a flow rate (Q) of 24 L/min, diameter (D) of 230 μ m, length (L) of 45 cm, viscosity (μ) of 3×10^{-3} Pa·s, and density (ρ) of 1060 kg/m³. The flow rate is converted to 4×10^{-5} m³/s, and the diameter and length are converted to 0.023 m and 0.45 m, respectively. Using these values, the cross-sectional area (A) is calculated to be 0.002 m². The velocity (V) is then determined to be 0.024 m/s, and the Reynolds number (Re) is calculated to be 195.599. The pressure drop (ΔP) across the system is calculated as 7.862 Pa or 0.001 psi.

Legend: Q: Flow rate; D: Diameter; L: Length; μ : Viscosity; ρ : Density; A: Cross-sectional area; V: Velocity; Re: Reynolds number; ΔP : Pressure drop.

Supplementary Table 2: Compliance Matrix

Ref.	Final Specification	Acceptable Outcome	Verification Method	Test Result	Pass/Fail	Notes
1.1	Device has pulsation in the femoral artery	Device pulses when running	Use Welch Allyn to verify system pulses between 2 pressures	See below	Pass	See below
1.2	Correct feedback when inserting the needle	The device correctly induces feedback when needle is inserted	Have doctor insert needle to verify correct feedback	See below	Pass	See below
1.3	Groin piece must be ultrasoundable	Vein and artery can be seen on ultrasound	Use ultrasound machine and verify with doctor that the image is correct	See below	Pass	See below
1.4	Groin piece must be easily replaceable	Groin can be easily replaced	Demonstration showing part replacement	See below	Pass	See below
1.5	Groin piece must be reused for at least 15 people	Groin can be reused by at least 15 users	Experiments with poking tube	See below	Pass	See below
2.1	System must decrease pressure over seven minutes unless balloon is placed	Pressure starts at 70/40 mmHg and decreases to zero	Use Welch Allyn pump to verify decrease in pressure	See below	Pass	See below
2.2	Balloon placement causes pressure in system to increase	Pressure increases to 110/70 mmHg +/- 10 mmHg	Use Welch Allyn pump to verify increase in pressure	See below	Pass	See below
2.3	Kickback is felt when balloon is placed and inflated	Kickback felt by user when pressure increases	Have doctor insert balloon to verify correct feedback	See below	Pass	See below
3.1	System must have maximum of 1 L of fluid in system	System has 1 L of fluid	Measure fluid with alternate container	See below	Pass	See below

4.1	Entire system will be portable and self-contained	Mannequin will be easily moveable, and content will stay in the mannequin	Move mannequin from one place to a new place	See below	Pass	See below
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The compliance matrix above describes the general design specifications, the specific outcome to address the specification, how this was verified, and a confirmation of a passing score under the pass/fail column. We were able to meet all specifications in our design, see notes below.

1.1 Device has pulsation in the femoral artery

The Welch Allyn clearly showed the pulsation between the two pulses at 70 and 40 mmHg.

1.2 Correct feedback when inserting the needle

The steps taken to show that this was accurate was letting a trauma surgeon test the system. He performed the entire REBOA procedure. We asked him a series of questions regarding the realism of the needle feedback. He liked the fluid jet, felt there was some resistance, but it had the correct feedback.

1.3 Groin piece must be ultrasoundable

The Humimic groin piece was ultrasoundable which was shown by a trauma surgeon testing it at UT Southwestern.

1.4 Groin piece must be easily replaceable

The groin was easily replaceable with the ball valve. This was shown by allowing a Trauma Surgeon to replace the groin, and testing that it was replaceable in a short amount of time. It also allowed minimum leakage.

1.5 Groin piece must be reused for at least 15 people

The groin could be reused if super glue was used at the point of puncture. This was tested over multiple insertions and shown that the groin can be resealed.

2.1 System must decrease pressure over seven minutes unless balloon is placed

The Welch Allyn clearly displayed the decrease in pressure over 7 minutes.

2.2 Balloon placement causes pressure in system to increase

A Trauma Surgeon placed the balloon during the procedure which increased the pressure to the targeted blood pressure. It was slightly higher than expected, but this was fine according to the trauma surgeon.

2.3 Kickback is felt when balloon is placed and inflated

A Trauma Surgeon placed the balloon while performing the procedure, and it was found that the system did have the correct feedback.

3.1 System must have maximum of 1 L of fluid in system

System holds a liter of fluid provided by the reservoir selected.

4.1 Entire system will be portable and self-contained

After placing the components in a self-contained box, the mannequin became portable and self-contained. It was able to move from one place to another

Supplementary Table 3: Comparison of the different parts present in each of the respective REBOA simulators

Parts Present*	TREBOA	Medalus ¹	PerfusionSim ²	Keller Study ³	Prytime ⁴	Walsh Study ⁵	VR	Syndaver ⁶	Cadaver	Animal
Plastic mannequin	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Thigh pad	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
Rubber hoses	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	n/a	yes	n/a	n/a
Electrical pump	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	n/a	yes	n/a	n/a
Valves	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	n/a	yes	n/a	n/a
Pressure monitor	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	n/a	yes	n/a	n/a
Sensors	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	n/a	n/a
Circuitry	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	n/a	n/a
Programing	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	n/a	n/a
Organs	no	no	yes	no	yes	no	n/a	yes	yes	yes
Ribs	no	yes	yes	no	yes	no	n/a	yes	yes	yes

*Information determined from product websites and conversations with sales personnel to the best of the investigator's ability.

Legend: N/a = not applicable, VR = virtual reality.

Supplementary Table 4: Comparison of the availability, safety, reliability, and efficiency in each of the respective REBOA simulators

	TREBOA	Medalus ¹	PerfusionSim ²	Keller Study ³	Prytime ⁴	Walsh Study ⁵	VR	Syndaver ⁶	Cadaver	Animal
Availability^A	high	high	low	high	low	high	low	low	low ³	low
Safe^B	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	exposure risk ⁷	exposure risk
Reliable^C	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Efficient^D	high	high	high	high	high	high	low	low	low ^{3,8}	low

Legend: A = High availability refers to the availability of the parts to build the model, or availability to easily purchase the item without requiring > 2 weeks waiting time for delivery or set up, otherwise the device received “low”. B = Safety refers to the REBOA simulation posing an exposure risk to the user. C = Reliability refers to evidence of the simulation being tested multiple times, and the design demonstrating the simulation would give a reasonably consistent experience. D = Low efficiency refers to low reusability (cadaver or animal models), or increased time required to set up and run the simulation (VR). VR = virtual reality.

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